

CHRONIC HEPATITIS, WHAT IS IT AND HOW TO CORRECTLY TREAT IT?

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Abstract. Hepatitis B (HB) is one of the main causes of chronic diffuse liver diseases throughout the world, observed in more than 350-400 million people, which is 5% of the world population. Of these, about 1.25 million HBV carriers live in the United States. In this population, the risk of developing cirrhosis, hepatocellular failure and carcinoma is high, and death is predicted in 25-40% of patients. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remains one of the largest viral pandemics. According to observations, from last 25-30 years in the United States, about 49% of all patients with hepatitis were infected with hepatitis A, 34% with hepatitis B, 15% with hepatitis C, and 2% with an unspecified form of hepatitis. The main risk factor for HBV transmission is sexual intercourse with infected or casual partners - 48% of known factors. HBV transmission during intravenous drug administration is 11%. There is still a large percentage of unknown causes of infection - 30%.

Keywords: viral hepatitis B, HbsAg, HbeAg, Anti-HBs, interferon, entecavir, lamivudine, Adefovir dipivoxil, telbivudine.

Characteristics of virus. HBV is a member of the Hepadnoviridae family containing deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) as part of the viral genome. The hepatitis B virus consists of an outer shell - HBsAg and NK or core - the core antigen of hepatitis B (Fig. 1), which surround DNA and DNA polymerase.

HBV is transmitted vertically, parenterally, sexually and through close contact, especially within families and among young children. Most infected adults and adolescents suffer an acute form, which can be not only classical, but also asymptomatic.

The acute form of infection is characterized by the detection of HBsAg antigen in the blood. Recovery is accompanied by elimination HBsAg in the blood and cessation of replication, the formation of a pool of HBsAb antibodies.

A small percentage (about 5%) of the acute form of the disease becomes chronic, and its diagnostic criterion is the presence of HBsAg in the blood for more than 6 months. Infection of newborns and infants from mothers is quite rarely clinically diagnosed, but in more than 90% of cases they develop a chronic form of hepatitis B. There is also a high risk of chronicity of the process in patients with immunodeficiency.

Figure 1. Structure of hepatitis B virus

Currently, there is a fairly high risk of HBV infection, so a thorough examination of sexual and family contacts, as well as all pregnant women, for the presence of HBsAg is necessary. A patient who has recently been diagnosed with hepatitis needs to undergo a full medical examination. Emphasis should be placed on identifying risk factors for the development of HBV infection, its combination with hepatitis C (HCV) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Factors that may complicate liver disease, such as alcohol consumption, should also be taken into account. It is necessary to carefully collect anamnesis in patients with hepatitis B and carcinoma, which includes clarification of sexual contacts and contacts in the family. It is also necessary to prevent infection of contact people, incl. using HBV vaccination (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Chronic Hepatitis B Testing and Management Algorithm

HBsAg is detected in the blood 2-8 weeks after infection and in most cases after 4 months. after infection disappears from the serum. HBeAg appears during the acute period of the disease for a short period of time. Its detection in chronic hepatitis or cirrhosis of the liver indicates the ongoing development and reproduction of the virus (Table 1).

As mentioned earlier, the most specific tests for detecting HBV DNA and the functioning of the virus in liver tissue are the detection of HBeAg, HBeAb. In patients with identified risk factors for HCV and HIV infection, studies are necessary to identify antibodies to their antigens.

The decision to perform a liver biopsy in patients with chronic hepatitis is controversial and there is currently no consensus on this issue. Increased aminotransferases, positive HBeAg, significant concentration of HBV DNA; these data are sufficient to initiate treatment without a biopsy. When a patient with normal aminotransferases has HBV DNA or a positive HBeAb but a negative HBeAg (suggesting the presence of some viral mutation), it is suggested that a liver biopsy is highly effective in guiding initiation of treatment.

Patient management. Patients with chronic hepatitis should be advised to reduce alcohol consumption to a minimum. It is also necessary to test their sexual partners, family members and people in contact with them for the presence of HBsAg and for HBsAb to identify those infected. Until HBsAb is detected in sexual partners and they are not vaccinated against hepatitis B, the need for contraception remains. Hepatitis A (HA) vaccination should be recommended for all patients with chronic liver disease. Testing for antibodies to GA before vaccination is quite expensive, but in some cases, they can reveal a previous infection.

In patients with chronic HBV, the risk of developing liver carcinoma is extremely high. Liver carcinoma within 4 months. doubles in size, is not covered by a membrane, tends to metastasize late and, due to the fact that the liver is an organ with a rich functional reserve, can be asymptomatic for a long time. Tumors detected in the preclinical phase, with a diameter of less than 5 cm, can be successfully treated with surgical treatment. Thus, for patients at high risk of developing liver cancer, it is rational to conduct screening studies and determine the tumor marker - α -fetoprotein (AFP) to detect carcinoma at an early stage. Screening studies of AFP and ultrasound of the liver, starting from 35 years of age, must be performed every 6 months. Patients at high risk of developing carcinoma need screening studies from the moment chronic hepatitis is detected.

HBsAg	Anti-HBs	Anti-HBc	HBeAg	Anti-HBe	Conclusion (diagnosis)
+	-	IgM	+	-	Highly infectious acute hepatitis B
+	-	IgG	+	-	Highly infectious chronic hepatitis B

+	+	IgG	-	+	Remitting or chronic hepatitis B with low infectivity****
+	+	+	+/-	+/-	Infection with two different HBV subtypes or current seroconversion. Rarely seen
-	-	IgM	+/-	+/-	Acute hepatitis or anti-HBc "window"
-	-	IgG	-	+/-	Old hepatitis B or HBsAg carriage with low replication
-	+	IgG	-	+/-	Remitting acute hepatitis B
-	+	-	-	-	Treated hepatitis B. Reaction to hepatitis B vaccine. Erroneous analysis

Hereinafter, the presence of the combination Ag in the abbreviation indicates that we are talking about a viral antigen. Thus, the abbreviation HBsAg stands for Hepatitis B superficial Antigen; **The presence of the prefix anti- denotes antibodies produced by the body to a specific antigen of the virus. Thus, the abbreviation anti-HBs refers to antibodies produced against HBsAg; *The abbreviation HBV-DNA, synonymous with HBV-DNA, stands for the DNA of the hepatitis B virus, and HCV-RNA stands for the RNA of the hepatitis C virus (the genome of the latter, unlike hepatitis B, contains ribonucleic acid, not deoxyribonucleic acid); ****If chronic hepatitis B is suspected, a PCR test for HBV-DNA should be performed.*

Table 1. Typical combinations of hepatitis B markers and corresponding clinical significance (diagnosis)

Treatment

The primary goal of HBV treatment is to stop the active phase of viral DNA replication. If it is achieved and recorded, the risk of complications and death is significantly reduced. FDA approved the following drugs for the treatment of hepatitis B: interferon- α , lamivudine, adefovir dipivoxil, entecavir, telbivudine.

Interferon. Interferons have immunostimulating properties and antiviral activity and immunostimulating properties.

Interferon- α is given as a subcutaneous injection and most patients can self-administer it. The standard dose for chronic HBV infection is 5 million IU daily or 10 million IU 3 times a week for 16 weeks for patients with HBeAg.

Many experts note that patients tolerate the regimen better with daily use. Interferon is a drug that has a myelosuppressive effect, and patients require regular testing to ensure timely detection of neutropenia and thrombocytopenia. When using interferon, it is possible to intensify existing or manifest hidden autoimmune disorders; therefore, all autoimmune diseases, with the exception of hypothyroidism, are a contraindication for such a course of treatment. In patients suffering from depression, exacerbation is possible. Interferon is an effective treatment for exacerbation of hepatitis, but it cannot be used in patients with decompensated liver disease (Child-Pugh class B or C), because in this situation, there may not be enough

intact liver tissue to restore its functions. However, there is evidence to suggest that patients with mutated HBV may benefit from treatment with interferon- α for 12 months or more.

Recently, 2 variants of pegylated interferon- α have been approved for the treatment of chronic hepatitis B: Pegasys (peginterferon- α -2a) and peginteron (peginterferon- α -2b). The advantages of these drugs are their prolonged action and administration once a week. Currently, studies are being conducted to determine the effectiveness of these drugs in chronic viral hepatitis.

Currently, the drug peginterferon (Pegasys), which is a complex of recombinant α -2a-IFN (Roferon A) with polyethylene glycol, is very promising for the treatment of hepatitis B, which makes the drug more resistant to the action of proteases and significantly prolongs its effect. Long-term removal of IFN from the body makes it possible to prescribe the drug once a week compared to standard treatment with IFN drugs.

Treatment with peginterferon in doses of 135 mg and 180 mg caused a stable positive response in patients with HBV. A study of the effect of peginterferon in the treatment of patients with liver cirrhosis of viral etiology showed that its effectiveness is higher than that of roferon A. After 6 months. After completion of therapy, patients with cirrhosis treated with peginterferon showed a sustained response. In monotherapy mode, Pegasys is used for 48 weeks.

When prescribing Pegasys, it is necessary to take into account that it interacts with theophylline; no interactions with other antiviral drugs have been identified.

Peginterferon- α -2b is a covalent conjugate of recombinant interferon- α -2b and monomethoxypolyethylene glycol, the site of PEGylation is histidine-34.

The cellular effects of peginterferon are due to binding to specific receptors on the surface of cells. By binding to the cell membrane, it initiates a sequence of intracellular reactions that include the induction of certain enzymes. Peginteron is prescribed subcutaneously at a dose of 1.0 to 1.5 mcg/kg once a week for 24-52 weeks. The dose is selected individually, taking into account body weight, effectiveness and safety of the drug. Patients with difficult-to-treat chronic hepatitis B caused by genotype C or D virus may require higher doses of the drug and a longer course of treatment to achieve a therapeutic effect.

Positive qualities of peginterferon:

- increased half-life due to decreased renal and hepatic clearance;
- high antiviral activity;
- prolonged action;
- reduction of antigenic and immunogenic activity;
- increased stability, constant concentration in the blood;
- resistance to proteolysis;
- increased bioavailability due to reduced losses during subcutaneous injection;
- reduced toxicity;
- possibility of individual dosing depending on body weight.

Lamivudine. Lamivudine is an orally administered nucleoside, the action of which is based on integration into the DNA chains of the virus, further preventing its

elongation, which prevents re-replication of the virus. Use of this drug at a dose of 100 mg/day has been shown to be extremely effective in reducing HBV DNA. After 3 years of continuous treatment with lamivudine, approximately one third of patients with HBeAg begin to produce HBeAb. This suggests shorter seroconversion induced by lamivudine compared with interferon- α . Patients with suspected mutated HBV who are HBeAg negative respond well to lamivudine therapy, but in most cases reactivation of the viral response occurs after discontinuation of the drug. As with interferon- α , high aminotransferases are a good prognostic sign. Although the drug is extremely well tolerated by patients, the main problem with its use is the resistance of some virus mutants to it. Approximately 15% of patients with chronic hepatitis B develop resistance to lamivudine after 1 year of treatment, and after 3 years this number reaches approximately 50%.

Adefovir dipivoxil. Adefovir dipivoxil (hepsera) is currently considered a modern drug for the treatment of chronic hepatitis B. This nucleotide analogue has been shown to be effective against both HBeAg-negative and HBeAg-positive chronic HBV infections, as well as against HBV infections that have become resistant to lamivudine. The standard dose of the drug is 10 mg/day, but when prescribing it, it is necessary to take into account renal function, because the main side effect of the drug is its nephrotoxicity. To date, only a few cases of resistance to Hepsera have been reported.

Entecavir. Entecavir (Baraclude) was recently approved for use in clinical practice. The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved this drug for the treatment of chronic HBV infection in March 2005 based on results from large studies that demonstrated a favorable safety profile and superior efficacy of entecavir (0.5 mg daily) compared with lamivudine (100 mg daily) in HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients with chronic hepatitis B [17, 18].

Entecavir is a cyclopentyl guanosine analogue with selective activity against HBV and low toxicity. According to preliminary results, entecavir, even at a low dose (0.1 mg daily), suppresses HBV replication [10]. When prescribing the drug at a dose of 0.5 mg/day. In patients with chronic HB caused by YMDD mutants, by 24 weeks of treatment, HBV DNA in the blood serum was absent in 50%, and with prescribing the drug at a dose of 1.0 mg/day. - in 75% of patients. In past and ongoing clinical trials, baraclude has demonstrated significant antiviral activity against both the "wild" strain of HBV (recommended dose 0.5 mg/day) and lamivudine-resistant strains (recommended dose 1 mg/day). By 96 weeks of antiviral therapy (AVT), the achievement of an undetectable HBV DNA viral load is recorded in almost 80% of HBeAg-positive patients (HBeAg seroconversion by this period is 32%). However, after cessation of treatment, a relapse of viremia is observed (a negative HBV DNA result after 24 weeks of observation decreases to 31%), while the rate of HBeAg seroconversion increases to 70%.

In 60% of patients with chronic hepatitis B with the development of resistance to lamivudine, the administration of entecavir is accompanied by complete normalization of ALT, and in 81% seroconversion of HBeAg is recorded. The undoubted advantages of entecavir include good tolerability, rare occurrence of adverse events and a low incidence of HBV genome mutations in the first 2 years,

amounting to 8%. Continuation of clinical studies will make it possible to clarify the incidence of resistance to entecavir with longer use.

Among the registered nucleoside analogues, entecavir has highly effective antiviral activity. The superiority of entecavir over lamivudine in the treatment of lamivudine-resistant HBV strains has now been confirmed. Prescription of entecavir at a dose of 1 g/day. after 96 weeks of use in HBeAg-positive chronic hepatitis B with lamivudine resistance, it resulted in aviremia (<300 copies/ml) in 30% of patients, HBeAg seroconversion in 16%. When treating patients with entecavir at a dose of 0.5 or 1.0 mg/day. the rate of reduction in HBV DNA viremia was 90 and 92.9%, respectively.

Entecavir at a dose of 0.5 mg/day. more active than lamivudine 100 mg/day. in the treatment of primary HBeAg-negative patients when used for 52 weeks: HBV DNA < 0/7 IU/ml in 90 and 67% after 48 weeks. AVT, HBV DNA < 300 copies/ml in 76 and 43% at the same period, while seroconversion of HBeAg-positive patients is 15 and 18%. The initial level of ALT and viral load do not affect the effectiveness of entecavir therapy. Based on the results obtained in three large clinical trials, it was concluded that entecavir is superior to lamivudine in the treatment of primary HBeAg-positive patients and HBeAg-negative patients and HBeAg-positive lamivudine-resistant patients with severe fibrosis or formed cirrhosis in relation to the dynamics of histological changes .

Entecavir is a potent inhibitor of hepatitis B virus replication and is active against lamivudine-resistant viruses. Other advantages of the drug include the ability to take it once a day and an improved safety profile. The study of the effectiveness of entecavir in chronic HB was carried out in accordance with a specially developed program and is currently the largest controlled study of the activity of antiviral drugs in this pathology. The main adverse events identified included headache, fatigue, diarrhea and dyspepsia. Entecavir became the fourth antiretroviral drug approved for use in chronic viral hepatitis B.

A number of drugs that are promising for the treatment of patients with chronic hepatitis B, in particular tenofovir, emtricitabine, clevudine, pradefovir and valtorcitabine, are currently undergoing clinical trials.

Telbivudin. The use of telbivudine (Sebivo) for the treatment of chronic hepatitis B was recently approved in Russia. It belongs to the group of nucleoside analogues; its antiviral activity consists of blocking the virus polymerase.

In preclinical studies aimed at clarifying the side effects of the drug, no significant toxic effects, carcinogenicity or effects on reproductive function were identified. In 2006, at a meeting of the American Hepatology Association, Lai C.L., Gane E., Liaw Y.F. et al. [15] presented data from a 2-year triple study of the effectiveness of telbivudine versus lamivudine (GLOBE) in chronic hepatitis B. The randomized trial included 1367 patients, of which the first group took telbivudine at a dose of 600 mg once a day, and the second group took lamivudine at a dosage of 100 mg once a day. According to study data for 104 weeks. Telbivudine demonstrated greater efficacy than lamivudine in the treatment of HBeAg-negative forms of chronic hepatitis B: viral DNA suppression was 82 versus 57%, respectively. In cases with HBeAg-positive breastfeeding, telbivudine was also demonstrated to be more

effective: after 104 weeks. viral seroconversion was 30% of patients in the telbivudine group compared with 25% in the lamivudine group. By the end of 1 year of therapy, all patients had significantly reduced absolute HBV DNA levels. In addition, complete clearance of HBV DNA from serum was more common among patients treated with telbivudine than in the lamivudine group (60 vs. 40% among HBeAg-positive patients and 88 vs. 71% among HBeAg-negative patients, respectively). One year after the start of therapy, resistance to telbivudine was observed in 3% of HBeAg-positive and 2% of HBeAg-negative patients versus 8 and 7% of patients in the lamivudine group, respectively. Analysis of data from the GLOBE study confirms that the earliest possible suppression of HBV is the determining factor for achieving optimal clinical effect [1, 15].

Lai C.L., Gane E., Liaw Y.F. et al. conducted a comparative study of the effectiveness of telbivudine and adefovir in 135 patients with HBeAg-positive chronic hepatitis B [16]. Patients were randomized into two groups, of which the first group was assigned to telbivudine and the second to adefovir for 24 weeks. In the first 24 weeks. study, telbivudine demonstrated higher efficacy (38% viral suppression compared with 12% with adefovir). Similar results were obtained in a further study of the second group of patients for 52 weeks: viral suppression in patients after “switching” from adefovir to telbivudine exceeded that in patients who continued taking adefovir.

Thus, telbivudine has been demonstrated to be more effective than lamivudine, which is the most commonly used drug for the treatment of chronic hepatitis B. It is extremely important that resistance to telbivudine develops less frequently than to lamivudine, especially when the effect of telbivudine therapy is achieved within 24 weeks.

In conclusion, we can add that with telbivudine therapy, viral suppression and ALT normalization are achieved more often than with adefovir therapy. Results from 1 year of a large 2-year phase 3 trial (GLOBE) of telbivudine versus lamivudine in chronic hepatitis were presented at the EASL meeting [10, 11]. It is noteworthy that the GLOBE studies showed that the effectiveness of telbivudine can be monitored in the early stages, namely at 24 weeks. It turned out that in patients who were PCR negative at 24 weeks, this indicator remained after 2 years.

Selection of patients for therapy

Treatment of chronic hepatitis B should be carried out only in patients with active virus multiplication, accompanied by high levels of HBV DNA. Since none of the available types of therapy will be effective during the immunotolerant phase of the infection, in a patient with normal aminotransferase levels, the above therapy should be given only if elevated liver enzymes are noted. However, if liver biopsy data in such patients demonstrate the development of serious liver damage, then they need to undergo active antiviral therapy. Once a decision is made about the need to treat chronic hepatitis B, appropriate therapy should be selected. Although the effectiveness of interferon- α and oral nucleoside and nucleotide analogues has not been proven in studies, their effectiveness has been practically confirmed. Interferon is prescribed by injection, but its use can cause significant side effects. The advantage

of tablets is safety and ease of use, but there is a possibility of developing tolerance to them.

Recommended treatment plan

It is assumed that any of the three drugs can be used as first-line therapy for chronic HBV infection. In a patient with HBeAg, especially if aminotransferases are more than doubled, it is initially recommended to use a standard 16-week course of interferon- α . In case of contraindications to the use of interferon associated with mental health and the presence of autoimmune processes, as well as in patients with decompensated liver diseases and those in whom it was not possible to achieve positive results within 6 months, alternative therapy should be recommended.

Treatment using tablet forms of lamivudine and adefovir dipivoxil is easily tolerated by patients and is quite simple to use, so it can be used with great success in patients with decompensated liver diseases. The main disadvantage of this type of treatment is its duration and the lack of an exact end date. In cases where HBeAg seroconversion occurs to produce HBeAb, consideration may be given to stopping treatment after a minimum of 3 months. However, after this there is a possibility of activation of the viral process. A longer course of treatment can lead to mutation of the virus and the emergence of forms resistant to therapy. It is preferable to limit the use of these drugs in patients at high risk of disease progression, therefore, it is recommended to perform a liver biopsy before administering drugs.

Conclusion. Currently, experience is being accumulated on the long-term use of the drug; there is a possibility that forms of the virus resistant to adefovir dipivoxil may develop an increasing trend. Since it is possible for resistance to one of the drugs to occur and sensitivity to another to remain, the use of combination therapy is rational, just as for HIV infection. An earlier study of combination therapy with interferon and lamivudine did not show a significant advantage over other treatments, but repeated studies of pegylated interferons and oral antiviral formulations showed different results. Consecutive use of nucleoside/nucleotide preparations after the emergence of resistance may lead to an increase in viral variants, which will ultimately lead to the need for a liver transplant, because the ineffectiveness of antiviral drugs leads to further progression of hepatitis B. Such patients are included in the liver transplant program.

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